

www.bjisrd.com

Training of highly qualified weightlifters

Zokirov Ravshanbek

State University of Physical Education and Sports of Uzbekistan

Abstract: *Weightlifting is a sport that requires strength, technique and endurance, in which athletes demonstrate their skills by lifting weights. Training for highly qualified weightlifters includes not only physical training, but also psychological and strategic training. In this article, we will talk about the training of highly qualified weightlifters, their composition and importance.*

Key words: *elite weightlifters, training, endurance, movement, athletes, fitness, recovery.*

Today, it is difficult to imagine a healthy generation without physical education and sports. Weightlifting plays a special role in strengthening their health and building their stature, especially through weightlifting training. Today, the correct organization of teaching and learning methodology and education based on innovative technologies are considered to be urgent issues of the day. Weightlifting is a type of sport in which athletes compete in weight lifting in two classic events - the deadlift and the deadlift. Such a competition program of weightlifters has been in force since 1972 in accordance with the decision of the International Weightlifting Federation. Until this time, weightlifters competed in triathlons - squatting, deadlifts and deadlifts. The advanced theory and practice of modern youth sports reliably proves that it is necessary to take into account age and gender, physical fitness characteristics, emotional state, as well as the material base in the training of athletes. The scientific and simple correctness of any newly proposed sports training method is determined not only by the speed of meeting the skill requirements, but also by the appropriateness of the age of this contingent of athletes. It is known that among the main physical qualities, strength is the most important for weightlifting has practical significance.

Athletics is one of the sports that is rapidly gaining popularity in our country. More than 5,000 people are involved in weightlifting across the country, almost half of them are girls. In addition, about 300 trainers are working throughout the Republic. Our athletes proudly raise the flag of Uzbekistan in the world arenas by participating in national and international competitions. Qualified trainers and teachers are training our weightlifters. Today, weightlifting sections are successfully operating in 15 training centers for Olympic and Paralympic sports across the Republic and in all regions of the Republic. Each region is holding its own championships, according to their results, the strongest

weightlifters will participate in the championship and cup of Uzbekistan, and the selected athletes will adequately defend the honor of Uzbekistan on the international stage. Training for highly skilled weightlifters needs to be planned and structured. Weightlifters use weights to build strength. These exercises often include squats, deadlifts, bench presses, and other basic lifting movements. Technique is very important in weightlifting. Athletes conduct special training to improve lifting techniques. This is necessary for perfect execution of movements such as snatch and clean and jerk. Endurance is also important for weightlifters. They engage in aerobic training to strengthen the cardiovascular system and improve their general physical condition. Recovery time between workouts is also important. Athletes take adequate rest to allow muscle recovery and injury prevention. Psychological preparation is also important for highly qualified weightlifters. They need to develop motivation and positive thinking to achieve their goals. Athletes make mental preparations to achieve their goals. This includes developing self-motivation and stress management skills, strategic planning and competitor analysis before competitions. This helps athletes to distribute their forces correctly. For highly skilled weightlifters, competitions are an opportunity to demonstrate their skills and show results. Participating in competitions is important for athletes to challenge themselves, set new goals and improve their performance. The results of the competitions affect the future training and preparation plans of the athletes.

The detailed development of the technology for training highly qualified athletes deserves great attention. This technology is deeply individualized and career oriented. In this regard, it is very important to solve the tasks of load regulation at different stages of preparation. The dynamics of the influence of certain metabolic functions on the level of special endurance of wrestlers by age is presented. It is necessary to take into account the influence of the rational use of various means and methods of training on the importance of bioenergetic functions, which determine the level of special endurance of wrestlers. However, the authors did not provide specific standards of optimal loads for training sessions. It is very important to know this in the optimal regulation of loads.

Psychological preparation is important to athletes for a number of reasons. This preparation helps to improve the mental state of athletes, achieve success in competitions and optimize overall sports performance. Psychological preparation allows athletes to manage stress and calm down during competitions. It helps to reduce nervousness and feel good before competitions. Psychological preparation allows athletes to control their emotions and make the right decisions during competitions. Improve yourself by analyzing your mistakes and learning from them. Psychological preparation helps athletes to properly focus on the competition process. Focus and achieve your goals during competition.

Psychological training together with physical training increases the overall performance of the athlete. Mental preparation helps to increase physical strength, because the state of mind affects physical activity. Psychological preparation allows athletes to increase self-confidence and achieve success in competitions. Correct assessment of one's abilities and confidence in them. Psychological preparation is important for athletes, improving their mental state, managing stress, increasing motivation and increasing their chances of success in competition. This preparation plays an important role in optimizing the general health and sports performance of athletes.

Conclusion:

The training of highly qualified weightlifters includes physical, technical, psychological and nutritional aspects. Their success is largely related to the effectiveness of the training plan, proper nutrition and psychological preparation. Weightlifting is a sport that requires not only strength, but

also discipline and endurance, and highly skilled athletes are constantly striving to improve themselves in order to achieve their goals.

References:

1. Barchukov I.S. Physical culture: textbook. manual for universities. - M.: "Unitidina", 2003.
2. Dvorkin L.S. Weightlifting // textbook for universities. - M., 2005.
3. Kerimov G.A. Sport sohasidagi ilmiy tadqiqotlar. T: "Zar qalarn", 2004.
4. Methodological recommendations for preparing coursework (thesis) for students of the Krasnodar State Institute of Physical Culture. - Krasnodar: KGIFK, 1986.
5. Bayazitov K.F. Optimization of the training process of high-grade weightlifters qualifications in the annual cycle / *dis. Ph.D. /*. 2009.